

PECULIARITIES OF COMPETENCE FORMATION IN STUDENTS' SELF-ASSESSMENT WHILE TEACHING L2

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Abstract:

This article presents a theoretical analysis of the advantages of students' self-assessment in the process of learning a foreign language. In the study, the effective ways of self-assessment in L2 foreign language classes, the opinions of researchers on this matter and the benefits of using it as an example of integrated reading skills were considered. It was analyzed that the organization of self-assessment by students helps to increase their grades and is aimed at the quality organization of the educational process.

Key words: self-assessment (SA), authenticity, integrated skills, reading, teaching L2, critical thinking, mainstream assessment, autonomous learner.

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Introduction

In the educational process, self-assessment (SA) is the organization of self-evaluation of the learner's activities and abilities in lessons and extracurricular situations (Black & Williams, 1998) problems such as increasing have been a topic of interest to many teachers. Even though English as a second language (L2) entered Uzbekistan at the end of the 19th century, in the 20th century, there was not the only way of teaching, assessing and learning it. In December 2012, based on presidential decree No. 1875, the introduction of the system of teaching, learning and assessment of foreign languages in the country according to the CEFR criteria.

To achieve progress, mentors lead students mainly work on themselves, the teacher's encouragement and the development of the self-assessment system by organizing autonomous education led to the increasing importance of studying issue of L2 and raised teachers' attention to the analysis of language systems. A specific assessment system was developed for L2 language learning, and based on the national assessment system, the organization, which is currently operating as the Knowledge Assessment Agency, operates as a system for assessing knowledge in L2, exact and natural sciences. It is aligned with the Common European Framework of Reference for L2 Teaching and Assessment (CEFR, Council of Europe) and continues to be integral to public education and higher education as required. Textbooks and other L2 learning materials are being developed in cooperation with local and foreign experts at the level of demand. Teaching English as L2 is a widely used foreign language in Uzbekistan, to advance self-assessment skills in the process of teaching it, and for the

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student to improve the quality of the acquired knowledge from one level to another in a short period of time. SA can be used in coincidence with other assessments such as traditional objective assessments, portfolios and peer assessments. According to the requirements of CEFR, the teachers are supporting the teaching of a foreign language in an integrated direction through communication.

As stated by several researchers of linguistics, it is recommended to include the use of self-evaluation system in educational programs (Nunan, 1988; Tarone & Yule, 1989); SA requires student-centered learning, self-monitoring and analysis, development of autonomous learner, critical thinker and creativity skills.

Despite the extensive coverage of SA, the practical application of SA in language classrooms is remarkably slow and SA has not been adopted in practice as expected (Bullock, 2011; Nikolov & Timpe-Laughlin, 2020). The fact that the use of SA in foreign language classes is low, partly because of the users' understanding and use of SA; for example, teachers may be skeptical about their students' ability to use SA, and students may not see SA as useful for their learning (Mäkipää, 2021).

Study objectives

We can consider the many advantages and intended uses of SA in order to create a framework for the effective use of SA by L2 teachers and students in SA education. In general, we can see that SA has two main objectives, which include assessment and improving the quality of education. The key focus is on the estimation system of SA according to Bailey (1998) who defined SA as "the procedures by which students assess their own language skills and knowledge" (p. 227), some scholars have argued that the level of self-assessment, develop an evaluation system in accordance with the curriculum. Another main focus is on improving the quality of SA in foreign language learning. This can be seen in Andrade and Valtcheva's (2009) definition: "a formative assessment process in which students raise their opinions about the quality of their work, assess the quality of their work, consider how well it reflects clearly defined goals or criteria, and are carried out accordingly" (p. 13). In the course of the execution of SA tasks, it is possible to monitor the portfolio, task results, achievements (in short, the results of many tasks and projects encountered in the educational process, as well as according to grades), it is an iterative process that can be summarized or observed in which self-assessment can be used to consider raising outcomes or changing direction Summarizing learning and achievement in lessons For Yuko Goto Butler (2022) a graphic representation showing the sequence of the acquisition process was tabulated and analyzed. A measurement for L2 learning from SA to show how the foreign language is improved for learning in general.

Methodology

Student self-assessment is a form of assessment that differs from traditional assessment and is not a substitute for mainstream assessment. The uniqueness of this is that its development is aimed at improving the quality of the educational process as a metacognitive element, and it also serves as a factor that increases students' self-confidence. It also helps to improve and develop foreign language skills, including self-evaluation and self-criticism, along with successful foreign language learning (Hedges, 2000). In addition, it helps students to set their own goals and develop several autonomous, independent learning skills such as observation, observation, and criticism (Brindly, 1989).

Some of the supporters of self-assessment point out that by focusing only on the teacher's assessment, the student may not notice his progress and cannot make an independent assessment (Ashraf and Mahdinezhad, 2015). According to Schwartz (1989), one of the advantages of self-assessment is that it allows students to observe and analyze how they see their peers' contributions to the group work process, student responsibility and engagement in the group, and students' thinking skills focused on progress.

It is possible to organize self-assessment through reading skills integrated with the L2 teaching process. For example, 'Traffic light systems' are an effective tool for students to take responsibility for their independent learning and identify the next step. A study by Leyla Zeyno Tosunoglu found that when a traffic light system was introduced to some students, they overestimated their abilities, while those with low self-confidence reported underestimating themselves. This allowed the teacher to intervene during the assignments during the lesson and to gain confidence or support from the students when needed. It was shown that the traffic light system allowed students to identify their strengths and areas for improvement, thus effectively influencing students' learning abilities. Importantly, it is important that the teacher guides the students by always pointing and noticing in the lesson, and it is important to carry out a specific and balanced approach. In particular, reading skills are a very important skill for L2 development and EFL is essential for students to perform successfully in higher education (Nasri & Biria, 2016). Of all the basic English skills, reading is the most important language skill in EFL settings (Nuttall, 1982).

In consonance with Puskorius (2011), reading comprehension means understanding the given main text. One of the important goals of teaching reading to students is the process of making meaning. Syatriana (2012) defines the importance of reading comprehension in the process of language learning as follows: "The important point is to understand what is read." It is an integrated thinking process that depends especially on the prior knowledge and comprehension skills of L2 learners. Speaking fluently in L2 includes, being able to use acquired knowledge, increasing vocabulary, understanding how words and chunks are related to each other, conveying thoughts fluently, and determining the author's point of view are important aspects of the language learning process.

Discussion

Thus, the ability to communicate through reading requires a holistic process that includes knowing the meaning of words and phrases, applying prior knowledge related to the text, and using metacognitive and cognitive methods to understand the text (Lotfi Sin & Siahpoosh, 2020). Effective readers must use strategies such as connecting text to prior knowledge, summarizing material, making inferences, and asking questions about texts to build comprehension during reading. Saito et al., (1999) suggested that teachers should develop the ability to discuss learning difficulties and concerns with students when assigning reading assignments to students. Students are encouraged to focus on the practical side of comprehension and find ways to read without literal translation to reduce difficulty.

L2 foreign language learners' use of self-assessment techniques has been shown to improve their motivation to study, reduce anxiety, and improve comprehension. It has also been shown that the benefits of teaching by organizing self-assessment in lessons are significant in developing EFL learners' reading motivation, anxiety and comprehension skills. On the other hand,

incorporating self-assessment into the learning process made students feel less anxious and less motivated. In addition, this led to an increase in reading comprehension performance.

The findings may have different implications for students, trainers, and curriculum developers. Second, it can provide EFL/ESL/ESP teachers and curriculum developers with useful insights into how to incorporate different teaching and assessment methodologies into lesson plans. Teachers can determine whether or not their students are engaged in the learning process by familiarizing themselves with the idea of framework, CL, and self-assessment. Language teachers are encouraged to change their instruction to one in which their students work collaboratively on a task and receive appropriate support from other qualified professionals. Based on the results of this study. In addition, encouraging problem solving and collaborative learning in the classroom can accelerate students' cognitive development. In fact, Vygotsky used the method of cooperative learning. Thus, it is recommended to view the classroom as a socio-cultural context in which active participation in the target language culture is encouraged. The results will help in creating materials for EFL students, especially for language learners at different levels. New textbooks should promote the idea that language learning is a process of active participation in the target language culture. The variety and complexity of the text types selected will increase with the students' ability level. Therefore, further studies with different gender and age groups are needed to confirm and strengthen these findings. Such studies will undoubtedly add to our knowledge of the nature of reading conception scaffolding.

Conclusion

Based on the results, self-assessment significantly improved EFL learners' motivation, anxiety, and comprehension. The results of this study help students understand the need for independent learning outside the classroom for continuous learning. This research can also help students to become independent and self-directed learners by allowing them to monitor their own progress, identify their own learning needs and gaps, and improve their own learning. allows you to accept responsibility for the results. This research may also be useful for teachers who like to help their students identify effective learning methods for themselves, as well as their strengths and weaknesses. Self-assessment checklists can provide teachers with detailed information about their students' learning gaps and failures, giving teachers useful feedback on their students which allows them to give comments and suggestions.

Despite our best efforts, research has limitations and shortcomings that cannot be avoided. The limited sample size of the study is the first limitation, and it is recommended that future studies include larger participants. Using only pre- and post-tests to collect data is another limitation. It is recommended that future research use a variety of tools to collect qualitative data that are more reliable and provide a deeper understanding of student learning. This study limited its application to reading skills, so it is recommended that future research examine how similar strategies affect other abilities and subskills. Further research is awaited to examine additional levels in addition to the intermediate level learners that were the subject of this study. Also, a single gender and specific age range was used to select all participants. Other researchers may use it among different genders and age groups. In addition,

different assessment methods such as peer assessment and portfolio assessment can be used in future studies.

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